

New Filler Composite System for PVC Window Frame

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ABSTRACT

In the paper, new reinforcing fillers for PVC window frame and/or other profiles are introduced. The one is a needle shaped calcium silicate - xonotlite ($6\text{CaO}\cdot 6\text{SiO}_2\cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$). Xonotlite is white and bulky powder. The crystal is usually 5 - 10 μm in length, 20 - 30 in aspect ratio and 30 - 70 m^2/g in surface area. The effects on plastics, especially PVC, are very functional. Particularly its high improving effects in modulus and thermal resistance are most noticeable as filler for PVC window frame. Besides these reinforcing effects, xonotlite does also many functional actions on PVC, for example, as hydrochloride and smoke retardants, as thermal and/or weathering stabilizer, as cross-link agent and so on. Another new reinforcing filler is ellestadite ($\text{CaO}-\text{SiO}_2-\text{CaSO}_4$ system). It is also needle shaped and shows a superior reinforcing effect on PVC, too. It is preferable in the respect that ellestadite is superior in the molding properties and the impact properties to xonotlite.

INTRODUCTION

Recently, polyvinyl chloride (PVC) window frame is widely used in Europe or North America, and it contributes much to saving energy because of its high adiabatic quality. Even Japan, it is on the market expansion now, but only in the coldest district in Japan such as Hokkaido. For the spread of PVC window frame in hotter districts of lower latitudes, however, it needs to develop more improved PVC window frame in the mechanical and/or thermal properties. Especially, the development of high modulus and low thermal expansion frame is urgently needed for being safely used in hotter districts.

Then, authors have started a developmental study to improve mechanical and thermal properties of PVC material by using inorganic fillers. As a preferable reinforcing filler for the improvement of PVC material, authors have noticed xonotlite, which is synthesized hydrothermally from calcium hydroxide and silica powder. The crystal is a needle or fibrous shaped as shown in Fig.1 and about 10 μm length. The crystal structure was revealed through the study of Mamedov and Belov (1). That is a double "Drierkette" of SiO_4 and is a kind of inorganic polymer. Authors have studied about the filler effects of xonotlite on plastics for several years. The reason why author notices xonotlite as a reinforcing filler for PVC window frame is that xonotlite shows various functional effects on

PVC as introduced in this paper. And also, ellestadite is introduced in the paper as another new reinforcing filler for PVC materials. Ellestadite is also needle shaped crystal and shows a superior improving effects in modulus and thermal properties as well. Ellestadite is a kind of apatite crystal synthesized by hydrothermal reaction of calcium hydroxide, silica powder and gypsum. Because this powder is not bulky as xonotlite, it shows a good molding properties when mixed with plastic powder. The both fillers, xonotlite and ellestadite, have being developed by MITSUBISHI MINING & CEMENT Co.Ltd. under co-research with authors.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of Xonotlite

Xonotlite was prepared by a hydrothermal reaction of calcium hydroxide and pure silica powder. The reaction temperature was 240 °C. After the reaction, the product was dried by a spray method. The photograph of xonotlite is shown in Fig.1. In the paper, the filler effects are shown about untreated and/or amino silane coupling agent treated xonotlite (SHINETSU KAGAKU KBM602, 1 wt% treated).

Test Materials

For mechanical and thermal tests, four kinds of material which differ from each other in filler content were prepared for untreated and silane coupling agent treated (SC-treated) xonotlite filled system.

The materials were produced by hot-roll mixing of xonotlite and PVC powder (NIHONZEON 103EP \bar{P} =1050). The roll temperature was 165 °C, and the roll sheets were piled up and hot-pressed to 3 mm in thickness.

The system is 25, 50, 75 and 100 PHR (Per Hundred Resin) in filler contents but unplasticized. As stabilizer, a mixture of buthyl tin-maleate and buthyl tin-mercaptide was used. Regarding ellestadite filled system, the materials were prepared by the same methods as in the case of the xonotlite filled system. But used ellestadite was prepared by MITSUBISHI MINING & CEMENT Co.Ltd..

Fig.1 Photograph of xonotlite crystal.

Mechanical Test

Tensile strength, Young's modulus, charpy impact strength, hardness and dynamic modulus were measured. These tests were carried out according to the JIS (Japan Industrial Standard) method in the air conditioning room under 23 °C and RH 50 %. INSTRON TESTER was used for the tensile and modulus tests. For impact test, charpy type tester of YAMATOHAKARI Co. was used, and TOYO-BAWLDWIN RHEO-VIBRON was used for dynamic modulus test.

Thermal Test, Combustion Test and Others

Thermal expansion coefficient and vicat softening point were measured as thermal tests. For the former 5 °C/min and 1 °C/min of elevation rate for the later were used respectively in the tests. The combustion tests were carried out using a small type of combustion furnace at 650 °C, under 500 ml/min of air stream. In the tests, mean velocity of combustion, maximum velocity of smoke evolution, maximum concentration of smoke evolution and hydrochloride (HCl) evolution rate (weight ratio of evolved HCl from the material) were measured. Besides these tests, TG and DTA, and pyrolytic gas analyses were carried out for each material, respectively.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mechanical Properties

First, the tensile properties of the xonotlite filled system are shown in Fig.2 and Fig.3. Fig.2 shows the ultimate strength at break. Xonotlite, especially SC-treated xonotlite, shows a high reinforcing effect. In the case of powder like filler, such high reinforcing effect in tensile strength as xonotlite is very rare case. Maybe it is because xonotlite crystal is fibrous and xonotlite brings a strong interaction in the interface between matrix and filler as mentioned later. Fig.3 shows the ultimate elongation rate upto break. The elongation of the xonotlite filled system extremely decreases from that of unfilled PVC. This means that xonotlite makes PVC a hard and glassy properties. Such a properties is rather useful for an improvement of molding accuracy. Then, in author's former study on the time and temperature dependences of the tensile strength about PVC - xonotlite composite system, it is observed that the glass transition temperature of the system rises with increase of xonotlite content (2). Xonotlite contributes much to the improvement of mechanical properties at higher temperature, too.

Next, the results of Young's modulus (E) are shown in Fig.4. The modulus remarkably increases with increase of xonotlite content. As was expected, the effect of SC-treatment is bigger in modulus, too. The very high reinforcing effect in modulus ranks with that of a glass fiber. Especially, it is desirable for window frame material to be high modulus.

Temperature Dependence of Modulus In summer, window frame become often 50 - 60 °C more. Therefore, for frame materials, an enough modulus and low expansion coefficient is necessary to stand such a higher temperature as near glass transition temperature of PVC. For that reason, it is very important for frame materials to examine temperature dependences of the modulus and also to make an improvement of modulus. The results about the temperature dependence of dynamic modulus (E') are shown for the xonotlite filled system in Fig.5. As shown in the figure, the modulus of unfilled polymer abruptly decrease in the glass transition region. However, the gradient of the xonotlite filled system become gentle with increase of xonotlite content. The relationships between the gradient and filler content are relatively shown in Fig.6. Here, the gradient G is shown as tangential value at maximum slope of E'. Namely, G value means a sharpness of the

Fig.2 Tensile strength of the xonotlite filled system (at break).

Fig.3 Ultimate elongation rate of the xonotlite filled system.

transition from glassy state to rubbery state. It is natural that a large one in G value is not so well in heat resistance as a small one. Also, in the Fig.6, the magnitude of transition is shown. Here, the magnitude D is shown as the difference between the moduli of glass state and rubbery state. When any slip or interaction does not exist on the interface between matrix and filler, a curve of D/D_0 or G/G_0 corresponds to the broken line which is connected between 1 of vertical axis and 1 of horizontal axis. Namely, the broken line is that of an ideal condition. When a slip exists on the interface, these curves come above the broken line. A good example is a polystyrene - aluminum powder system (3). On the contrary, when a free motion of matrix molecules is restrained by filler, curves come under the broken line. From the figure, it is evident that the free motion of PVC matrix is remarkably restrained by xonotlite. A strength of interaction between matrix and filler can be estimated from a degree of rise of glass temperature which is caused by filler (4). In the case of the xonotlite filled system, an extent of the interaction, namely the thickness of PVC matrix restrained by xonotlite, is about 70 - 80 Å (5). That of SC-treated xonotlite is about 150 Å. After all, the strong interaction between PVC and xonotlite contributes much to the improvement of mechanical and/or thermal properties of the system. Then, the relative moduli at glass state and rubbery state are respectively shown in Fig.7. As shown in the figure, it is very noticeable that the improving rate in modulus at higher temperature (rubbery state) is extremely large. The fact is one of the reasons why author strongly recommends xonotlite as a reinforcing filler for PVC window frame.

Fig.4 Young's modulus of the xonotlite filled system.

The results of impact test are shown in Fig.8. As shown in the figure, the impact strength of the xonotlite filled system is very inferior to that of unfilled PVC. As a matter of fact, this is the most demerit in the system. Therefore, a consideration must be taken to make a high impact compound for PVC window frame

Fig.5 Temperature dependence of storage modulus E' of the xonotlite filled system.
 1- unfilled PVC 2- 20 PHR
 3- 40 PHR 4- 60 PHR
 5- 100 PHR 6- 150 PHR

Fig.6 Effect of xonotlite on relative gradient (G/G_0) and magnitude (D/D_0) of the transition from glassy to rubbery state. Broken line is that of an ideal condition on the interface between filler and matrix.

of this system. Now, authors are doing experiments about addition effect of impact improving agent such as chlorinated polyethylene, EVA, acryl-VC co-polymer and so on. Maybe this problem will be solved before long.

Fig.9 shows the surface hardness of the materials. The hardness remarkably increases with increase of xonotlite content, especially the SC-treated system shows higher values. Of course, the improvement in hardness is a big merit for PVC window frame or profiles.

Thermal Properties

Following the mechanical properties, the thermal properties of the xonotlite filled system are discussed. First, the results of vicat softening point of the system are shown in Fig.10. As shown in the figure, an extreme rise in the softening point is observed with filling of xonotlite. Also, the SC-treated xonotlite is excellent in the improvement of thermal resistance. An improvement of 20 °C more is easy available. And also, it is understood from Fig.11 that the xonotlite filled system shows a strong resistance to compression or deformation at higher temperature. The figure shows the thermal compression rate under a constant weight at 100 °C. The compression rate decreases so much with filling of xonotlite.

Next, the results of thermal expansion test are shown in Fig.12 and Fig.13. Fig.12 shows the thermal expansion coefficient of the xonotlite filled system at 35 °C and 55 °C. The thermal expansion coefficient is remarkably decreased with filling of xonotlite. For example, the value of 50 PHR filled one is just half of that of unfilled PVC. Fig.13 shows the thermal expansion rate from 30 °C to 60 °C. To speak in more plain terms, for example, 1 m length of a rod of PVC (unfilled) expands about 26 mm when temperature rised from 30 to 60 °C. While, the expansion of 50 PHR filled one is only 13 mm. Surely, xonotlite is very superior to other fillers, such as calcium carbonate, talc, clay and so on, in the retarding effect of thermal expansion.

Fig. 7 Relative storage modulus (E') at glassy and rubbery state. (untreated xonotlite)

Fig. 8 Charpy impact strength of the xonotlite filled system.

Fig. 9 Vickers hardness of the xonotlite filled system.

Fig.10 Vicat softening point of the xonotlite filled system.

Fig.11 Thermal compression rate under a definite weight at 100°C of the xonotlite filled system.

Fig.12 Thermal expansion coeff. of the xonotlite filled system.

Fig.13 Thermal expansion rate from 30°C to 60°C of the xonotlite filled system.

Combustion Properties

The results from combustion tests are tabulated in Table 1. But the values of the filled system are shown relatively to unfilled PVC. The combustion rate become slower with filling of xonotlite. Also, the both of smoke evolution rate and smoke concentration decrease with increase of xonotlite content. It is worthy of attention as one of the functional properties that xonotlite has a high smoke retarding ability. Further merit of xonotlite is that xonotlite retards well an evolution of hydrochloride (HCl) as shown in the last item. The retarding effect on the both of smoke and hydrochloride is surely a big merit for PVC window frame or other housing materials. Because, when PVC materials burned, the most undesirable problem is an evolution of a lot of smoke and hydrochloride. Therefore, xonotlite can be recommended as very useful retardant for the both. How is xonotlite able to retard the both well? It is because xonotlite reacts with PVC at temperature of 200 °C or more, and catches chlorine from PVC. After that, at once, PVC is crosslinked between its molecules. (Therefore, the filled system become hard fusible with heat treating.) Consequently, a formation of conjugated double bonds is retarded, and aromatic gases decrease in the pyrolytic produced gases. A series of this process makes PVC a decrease in smoke, after all. (6,7)

Table 1 Combustion properties of xonotlite filled system.
(Test temperature : 650 °C)

Filler Cont. (PHR)	Combustion Rate	Smoke Evolution Rate	Smoke Concentration	HCl Evolution Rate
0 (PVC)	1	1	1	1
40	0.81	0.63	0.51	0.67
100	0.59	0.34	0.17	0.04

As proof of the reaction between xonotlite and PVC, the TG and DTA data are shown in Table 2. The weight loss in the first step of TG is caused by evolution of hydrochloride. A start of the weight loss differs from each other in the xonotlite content. The start shifts to higher temperature side with increase of the content. This is because xonotlite catches chlorine first, and after that the rest chlorine evolves in the form of hydrochloride later. On DTA, unfilled PVC shows only endo-thermic peaks, while the xonotlite filled system shows strong exo-thermic peak in the 1st step of TG because of the reaction between PVC and xonotlite. The reaction may occur a little when molded. Anyway, it may be thought that the strong interaction between PVC and xonotlite is caused by a chemical affinity between the both.

Table 2 The start- and end temperature of HCl evolution and the DTA peak temperature in the first step of pyrolysis of the system.

Filler Cont. (PHR)	Range of First Step in TG (°C)		DTA Peak Temperature (°C)	
	Start	End		
0 (PVC)	226	335	-286, -306	(endo-thermic)
5	248	332	+282	(exo -thermic)
10	264	330	+282	(exo -thermic)
20	272	328	+282	(exo -thermic)

Mechanical and Thermal Properties of PVC - Ellestadite System

Subsequently, the mechanical and thermal properties are discussed briefly about the ellestadite filled system. As shown in Fig.14, the ellestadite is also needle shaped crystal about 5 μm in length. The aspect ratio is about 10 and the surface area is about 2 m²/g. First, the mechanical properties are shown in Fig. 15 and 16. Fig.15 shows the results of tensile tests. As shown in the figure, ellestadite is inferior in the reinforcement of tensile strength to xonotlite. But the tensile elongation remarkably decrease with increase of the content. On the other hand, the Young's modulus is extremely improved as well as in the case of xonotlite as shown in Fig.16. Further, a very interesting point is that the impact properties is also improved with filling of ellestadite. From the figure, the impact strength becomes maximum at about 25 PHR content. In this respect, ellestadite is far better than xonotlite.

Next, the results of thermal properties of the system are shown in Fig.17 and 18. Fig.17 shows the vicat softening point. As well as xonotlite, ellestadite brings a remarkable rise in softening point. As shown in Fig.18, ellestadite is also advantageous to the retarding of thermal expansion. From these results, ellestadite

Fig.14 Photograph of Ellestadite.

is nearly equal to xonotlite in the improvement of thermal properties. Of course, a silane coupling agent treatment on ellestadite is useful for more improvement of these properties. Regarding the combustion properties, it is not yet examined, but can be expected the retarding effect. Ellestadite is somewhat inferior in the mechanical reinforcing effect, except for impact properties, to xonotlite. But more profitable point of ellestadite is that it has far improved workability of molding and dispersibility in matrix than xonotlite.

In filler and/or plastic industry, xonotlite or ellestadite is not familiar yet, however, they are surely useful and recommended as mechanical and thermal improving filler for PVC window frame or other profiles and other plastics, too.

Fig. 15 Tensile strength and elongation rate of the ellestadite filled system. (untreated)

Fig. 16 Young's modulus and impact strength of the ellestadite filled system. (untreated)

Fig. 17 Vicat softening point of the ellestadite filled system.

Fig. 18 Thermal expansion coeff. of the ellestadite filled system.

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